

ISic1352

I.Sicily inscription 1352

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Alex Antoniou,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di

Catania, inventory 258

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Ἐνθάδε κ[εῖται]

2. Εὐπλουτ[ορζήσας]

3. ἔτη δεκ[α]

Apparatus

Korhonen 2004

Translation (en)

Here lies Eupoloutos, having lived for ten(?) years.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492965

EDCS 39101730

PHI 140854

PHI 316266

Bibliography

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic1352. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4353519>